

CHARACTERISATION OF BOND STRENGTH IN OVERMOULDED HIGH-PERFORMANCE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the bond strength of a carbon fibre fabric-reinforced polyaryletherketone (PAEK) overmoulded with a short carbon fibre filled polyetheretherketone (PEEK) is characterised experimentally. Rib-on-plate coupons are manufactured and specimens are prepared for pull-off testing from different locations with the coupon. Results of reference configuration are compared to those with varied manufacturing parameters. Configurations chosen in order to alter the residual stress state showed no significant effect, while varied injection speed and temperatures of melt and laminate has noticeable effects. The most significant effect was seen at specimens with a weld line within the rib, where strength was reduced by > 50 % compared to the reference configuration.

1 INTRODUCTION

Overmoulding of continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic laminates with short fibre-reinforced injection moulding compound is increasingly gaining attention in the industry and academia. The technology has been introduced successfully in the automotive sector. Currently, possible application also in the aerospace sector is investigated. This requires not only the use of other high-performance materials which may be more difficult to process. There is also a stronger demand in understanding the mechanical behaviour of the overmoulding bond when considering primary aircraft structures for instance. Yet, there is no standard test method for determining the strength of an overmoulded joint. Also limited data is available on the bond strength of a material system based on polyaryletherketone (PAEK) polymers being reinforced with carbon fibres [1], [2]. Therefore, this study aims at the characterisation of the bond strength of such high-performance material system. An overview of recently proposed test methods is given in [3]. The authors also describe the development of suitable coupons for shear and tensile testing of the overmoulded interface. The tensile test approach using a rib-on-plate coupon is used in this study. In order to study the effects of manufacturing parameters, several configurations are tested with one parameter being varied compared to the reference configuration.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The material system used in this study comprises commercial grades for both the injection moulded part and the laminate insert. The laminate is made of Toray TenCate Cetex® TC1225 RTL, a polyaryletherketone (PAEK) reinforced with a 5 harness satin fabric of T300JB 3K carbon fibre [4]. The injection moulding compound is VICTREX® PEEK 90HMF40, a polyetheretherketone (PEEK) filled with 40 wt.% short carbon fibres [5].

According to the datasheets, both matrix polymers are compatible and suitable for overmoulding. While PAEK and PEEK exhibit comparable mechanical properties, the melting point of PAEK is 38 K lower. This allows for overmoulding with a lower preheating temperature of the laminate insert. [4], [5]

2.2 Coupon and mould design

In this study, a rib-on-plate coupon is used for characterising the overmoulding bond strength. The cross sectional dimensions of the coupon are depicted in Figure 1. The coupon has a length of 240 mm. Sections with a length of 25 mm are prepared from the coupon as pull-off test specimens. The development of this and other coupon geometries are described in more detail in [3].

Figure 1: Cross sectional dimensions of rib-on-plate coupon

The mould has a cold runner system with a selector element that allows filling the cavity either from one end of the rib or from both. In the latter case, which is depicted in Figure 2, a weld line is formed in the middle. The temperature of the steel mould is controlled using an oil temperature controller.

Figure 2: Rib-on-plate coupon with cold runner system and optional 2-sided gate

2.3 Coupon manufacture

Laminate insert preparation

The laminate material as supplied by the manufacturer is fully consolidated and consists of 8 fabric plies with a $[0,90]_8$ layup. Using a circular saw, the inserts are prepared by cutting carefully the larger laminates to the required dimensions.

Overmoulding

Prior to overmoulding, all laminate inserts are preheated to 220 °C in a convection oven next to the injection moulding machine. The manufacturing cycle of a coupon begins with taking an insert out of the oven, cleaning its surface by wiping it with acetone and quickly placing it into the open mould. This manual step takes about 5 ± 1 s.

After insert placement the mould is closed and the injection process is started. It takes about 10 s until the melt arrives on the insert. Filling is followed by packing, cooling, and ejection. The ejected coupons are manually transferred back into the convection oven to prevent rapid cooling to ambient temperature and support relaxation of the residual stresses. A complete cycle takes about 70 to 80 s in total. Unless noted otherwise, the convection oven is turned off two hours after manufacturing the last coupon, kept closed in order to cool the coupons slowly and give time to relax the thermal stresses due to different thermal expansion behaviour of both materials.

Manufacturing parameters

The coupons are manufactured under several configurations of manufacturing parameters. Those of the reference configuration *A* are listed in Table 1. In order to investigate the effect of manufacturing parameters on bond strength, these are varied according to Table 2 and denoted as configurations *B* to *I*.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Laminate insert temperature	T_{insert}	220 °C
Mould temperature	T_{mould}	220 °C
Melt temperature	T_{melt}	400 °C
Packing pressure	$p_{packing}$	50 MPa
Injection speed	$v_{injection}$	50 mm/s
Time of insert residing in mould before injection	$t_{in-mould}$	10 s
Number of gates	n_{gates}	1
Cooling condition after ejection	<i>Cooling condition</i>	2 h at 220 °C, then natural cooling to 23 °C

Table 1: Manufacturing parameters of reference configuration *A*

The temperature at which the interface is formed is considered as one of the most important parameters because interdiffusion of molecules is a highly temperature-dependent phenomenon [1]. Therefore the temperatures of both melt and insert are to be varied. Melt temperature is controlled relatively easy by setting the barrel and nozzle temperatures accordingly. Hence, configurations *B* and *C* involve higher and lower melt temperature respectively. The laminate temperature should result mainly from the preheating oven temperature. However, measurements with an infrared camera during preliminary tests revealed that the surface temperature of the insert rapidly decreases to about 180 °C within the few seconds required for cleaning and transfer into the mould. Since the set mould temperature is equal to that of the oven, the heat transfer from the mould to the insert should result in 220 °C at the insert surface after a sufficiently long period of time. Therefore in configuration *D*, an additional waiting time of 20 s is introduced between mould closure and filling. This results in 30 s passing until the melt arrives at the laminate.

Process-induced residual stresses at the interface could reduce the usable strength reserve of an overmoulded structure. Residual, internal stresses in the moulded component are inevitable as in every standard injection moulding process. Packing pressure is often varied to alter the residual stress state and resulting warpage and spring-in deformations. Combining two materials with different coefficients of thermal expansion and different relaxation behaviour should introduce additional thermal stresses, particularly at the interface. As thermomechanical material properties cannot be altered, packing pressure is varied in configuration *E* to study the effect of process-induced residual stresses at the interface. In another attempt to vary the internal stress state, the coupon of configuration *F* is not put back into the oven for tempering for at least 2 h. Instead, the coupon is cooling naturally at an ambient temperature of 23°C directly after ejection.

Higher injection speeds could be beneficial to the bond strength if higher melt shear rates lead to higher viscous heating and hence higher temperature at the interface. Higher and lower values than the reference are tested in configurations *G* and *H*.

Avoiding weld lines can be impossible when complex geometries are moulded. At a weld line forming across a rib, the short fibres should not be aligned in the longitudinal rib direction anymore. Instead, the fibres should be oriented predominantly perpendicular to the interface. Configuration *I* is manufactured to study the effect of such a weld line on bond strength.

Configuration	Varied manufacturing parameter	Value
<i>A (Reference)</i>	-	-
<i>B</i>	T_{melt}	420 °C
<i>C</i>	T_{melt}	380 °C
<i>D</i>	$t_{in-mould}$	30 s
<i>E</i>	$p_{packing}$	20 MPa
<i>F</i>	<i>Cooling condition</i>	naturally to 23 °C
<i>G</i>	$v_{injection}$	25 mm/s
<i>H</i>	$v_{injection}$	100 mm/s
<i>I</i>	n_{gates}	2

Table 2: Manufactured configurations of rib-on-plate coupon

2.4 Preparation of test specimens

For testing the bond strength under predominantly tensile loading conditions, a rib-pull-off test is performed. Therefore, the overmoulded rib-on-plate coupons are cut into shorter specimens. With a circular saw and slow cutting speed this is done carefully not to induce damage at the interface. The prepared specimens measure 25 mm in length. Up to five specimens are obtained from one coupon. However, the results shown here comprise only the first, third and fifth position. The specimens are numbered with roman small letters ranging from *i* next to the gate up to *v* at the opposite end of the rib. Sections in between adjacent specimens are available for investigation of the interface morphology using optical microscopy. These are numbered alphabetically from *a* to *f* as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Positions of specimens for rib-pull-off testing (pos. i to v) and optical microscopy (a to f) rib-on-plate-coupon

2.5 Rib-pull-off test

The rib-pull-off tests are carried out with a Zwick Z250 universal testing machine. While the rib is clamped using wedge grips, a specially designed fixture clamps the laminate of the specimen. The fixture consists of a steel frame being connected to the moving crosshead of the testing machine. The frame has a slot being 10 mm wide, which is wider than the rib foot. Through this slot, the rib protrudes and is clamped by wedge grips outside the frame. After tightening the wedge grips and thereby positioning the specimen laterally, the laminate is being pressed against the inside of the frame using a screw-driven wedge clamp. Figure 4 shows the fixture schematically.

As the quasi-static test starts, the crosshead moves with a constant speed of 2 mm/min. A 200 kN load cell is used to measure the force. Both pull-off force and crosshead displacement are recorded digitally. The test ends after complete separation. A gap in the laminate fixture allows capturing images of the interface at one of the end faces of the rib using a digital camera. These may help identifying initiation and growth of cracks.

Figure 4: Schematic of the specimen fixture used for the rib-pull-off test

2.6 Optical microscopy

Sections of the rib-on-plate specimen are cut from different locations along the rib. These are ground and polished for microscopy imaging. Extra care is taken in these steps not to damage the specimen. Single images are taken with an optical microscope ZEISS Axioplan. The device software automatically stitches multiple images to create an overview image covering the whole cross section of the interface.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Optical microscopy

Microscopy images are prepared from several specimens showing the cross section of the coupon. In Figure 5, two images are shown exemplarily. These are taken from a coupon of configuration *H* at two locations. Figure 5 (a) is taken from beginning of the rib, with a distance from the gate of 20 mm. Figure 5 (b) is taken from the end of rib with a distance from the gate 220 mm and 20 mm away from the end of the flow path.

Figure 5: microscopy images of the cross section of the rib-on-plate-coupon at different locations: 20 mm away from the gate (a); 220 mm away from gate and 20 mm away from the end of the flow path (b)

3.2 Pull-off tests

Six specimens are tested for each position and configuration except configuration *I*. There, at pos. iii only five specimens could be tested because the sixth was destroyed during preparation. For configuration *I*, pos. v is not tested because it should be identical to pos. i. The recorded values of force versus crosshead displacement are shown in Figure 6. Each plot contains the results for one configuration, where different line colours represent the three tested specimen positions within the rib.

The pull-off force rises linearly for the first 0.1 mm. The further evolution of the force-displacement curves is qualitatively different among the specimens. One typical shape is that the slope remains constant up to 0.2 mm followed by a decrease of slope followed by a large drop of the pull-off force, often resulting in complete separation of the specimen. Configurations *A*, *B*, *F* and *E* exhibit predominantly this behaviour. Another typical shape of force-displacement curves is an increase of slope following the initial region of constant stiffness. The slope remains nearly constant up to 0.2 mm of crosshead displacement. After that, a rapid drop of pull-off force in the range of -100 N occurs. This is followed by a nearly complete recovery of slope. Then the slope remains nearly constant until either complete separation or another sequence of dropping force and recovering stiffness. However, if a second drop and recovery occurs, this is spread over a larger range of displacement compared to the first. Configurations *C*, *D*, *G*, and *H* show this behaviour. The phenomenon of the second drop and recovery are observed only from tests of pos. iii and v of config. *D*, pos. i and iii of config. *G* and a single specimen from pos. i of config. *H*. A unique pull-off behaviour is observed at pos. iii of config. *I*.

Figure 6: Force-displacement curves of tested configurations and specimen locations within the rib; (a): reference config. A; (b): config. B with $T_{melt} = 420\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; (c): config. C with $T_{melt} = 380\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure 6 (continued): Force-displacement curves of tested configurations and specimen locations within the rib; (d): config. *D* with $t_{in-mould} = 30$ s; (e): config. *E* with $p_{packing} = 20$ MPa; (f): config. *F* cooled to 23 °C naturally after ejection

Figure 6 (continued): Force-displacement curves of tested configurations and specimen locations within the rib; (g): config. *G* with $v_{injection} = 25$ mm/s; (h): config. *H* with $v_{injection} = 100$ mm/s ; (i): config. *I* with $n_{gates} = 2$ creating a weld line at position iii

4 DISCUSSION

In the microscopy images it can be seen that for locations close to the gate the interface appears intact, whereas at positions far from the gate, cracks are opened from both ends of the interface. The cracks are typically 100 – 200 μm long. At the positions close to the gate, there is a little groove in the laminate on each side of the rib foot. It is assumed that these originate from a ridge on the mould surface, where the parting plane is identical with that of the interface. However, the groove is not present at the far-from-gate locations. A possible explanation could be that closer to the gate the maximum temperature seen by the laminate material is generally higher than at far from the gate. This assumption is supported by the apparently weaker bond at the edges of the rib foot far from the gate. Weaker bonds are thought to be formed if the maximum temperature there was not sufficient to facilitate a complete interdiffusion across the interface. Interdiffusion is expected to happen nearly instantly if both joint parts are fully molten. In that case, the laminate surface would probably show imprints of surface features of the mould surface. However, apart from the cracks the inner quality of the interface region appears to be good as no voids can be seen.

During the pull-off tests, it is observed that failure initiates at the edges and cracks grow towards the centre of the rib foot. This is explained by the bending deformation of the laminate and consequently a peeling motion during detachment of the rib. Additionally, due to the butt joint design, a considerable stress concentration should be present at the edges. During opening and growth of a crack, energy is dissipated. A stronger bond should lead to higher dissipated energy and consequently higher forces measured.

Assessing the force-displacement curves of reference configuration *A*, it is interesting that pos. *i* tends to fail at higher forces than the other positions and the apparent stiffness is also higher. Following the above mentioned thoughts on the relation between bond strength and measured forces, this phenomenon may indicate that the bond quality at positions close to the gate is better. This appears plausible when thinking of a higher amount of melt flowing over the interface region, bringing more heat into the laminate surface.

Comparing configurations *A*, *B* and *C* which are manufactured with different melt temperatures, it can be seen that the difference between pos. *i* and the others is more pronounced the higher the melt temperature was. In fact, it seems that the slope of the curves at pos. *i* is not affected by the melt temperature, but at pos. *iii* and *v* it decreases with increasing melt temperature. Another remarkable fact is the higher displacement at break for lower melting temperatures. These effects could be a result of higher internal stresses when a higher melt temperature is used. However, further efforts are required to clarify the causalities.

Configuration *D* differs from *A* only in a longer waiting time between mould closure and begin of injection. Following the considerations from the test design, this should lead to a higher surface temperature of the laminate insert. However, verification by direct temperature measurement using thermocouples closely under the laminate surface is complicated because the mould is designed to shut of the cavity not against the insert. Hence the laminate is not accessible from the outside when the mould is closed. Nevertheless, the effect of a presumably 40 K higher surface temperature on the force-displacement curves is remarkable. Comparing Figure 6 (a) and (d) one can see that specimens of config. *D* failed at displacements twice as high as those of config. *A*. Moreover, the drop and recovery of stiffness is only present in config. *D*. Assuming a higher laminate surface temperature, the bond especially at the edges of the rib foot should be stronger. During the tests the exact first crack location could not be identified due to little space in the fixture. However, the authors' hypothesis is that crack opening and early growth occurs more gradually if the bond is weaker and the polymer has been given not enough time to fully crystallise. Vice versa, a stronger bond, possibly facilitated by a higher degree of crystallinity at the interface, could show a more brittle crack growth behaviour. However, further investigations on the matter are necessary.

The lower packing pressure applied in configuration *E* shows no significant effect on the force-displacement curve, if compared with *A*. Further tests with larger variations should be carried out to clarify the suggested independence of packing pressure and bond strength. Similarly, the skipped tempering in configuration *F* seems to have just little effects. From the results, one might recognise a small reduction of displacement at break.

The variation of injection speed yields interesting results. The authors did not expect seeing higher forces and displacements at break as well as the drop and recovery of stiffness for configurations *G* and *H* with lower and higher injection speeds respectively, but not for the reference configuration *A*. Injection speed surely affects the moulding process and material properties in many ways, partly also in an adverse manner. For example, higher injection speeds lead to stronger shearing of the melt, in turn leading to more dissipated heat. More heat should be beneficial to the bond strength. Higher injection speed also leads to more oriented molecular chains and different fibre orientation. This could change the thermomechanical material properties in a way that reduces or enhances residual stresses acting against the interface. But the residual stress state is also very dependent on the part geometry and other factors, making it impossible to give profound conclusions here. Additional experiments with injection speeds between 25 and 100 mm/s are suggested.

The most remarkable effect on force-displacement curves is seen in configuration *I*, more precisely at pos. iii. There a weld line is formed and the strength is reduced dramatically. Microscopy images show that most of the interface is detached. This is explained by no considerable melt flow over the interface and consequently only little heat transferred from melt to laminate. Moreover the short fibre orientation there is predominantly perpendicular to the interface which should lead to a stronger mismatch between thermal expansion coefficient of laminate and moulded part. The additional thermal stresses will negatively affect the testable strength. A similar reduction of bond strength is expected at the end of the flow path in any overmoulded structure. However, in this study the specimen being closest to the end of the flow path, was already 20 mm away from it, which is why this could not be investigated in further detail.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, rib-pull-off tests were carried out with specimens which have been manufactured under varied manufacturing parameters. Many interesting observations could be made, needs for further experiments and analyses are identified. While some manufacturing parameters showed no significant effect, others largely affected the response of the pull-off test. For instance on the one hand it was found, that an additional waiting time between mould closure and begin of injection doubled the displacement at break and increased the force at break by a factor of approx. 1.3. On the other hand, skipping the tempering and subsequent slow cooling reduced the force and displacement at break to just a little extent. The largest effect was observed on specimens with a weld line in the moulded rib. There, the strength is reduced dramatically so much that one specimen already failed during preparation. A major conclusion from this study is that crack initiation and growth are dependent on the local bond strength. Differences in the bond strength near the edges of the rib foot can possibly be identified from the slope of the force-displacement curves in the early phase of the test. However, further experiments and a more detailed analysis of the evolution of specimen failure is required.

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